

Polymetallic complexes. Part-LXXV. Cobalt-, nickel-, copper-, zinc-, cadmium- and mercury(II) with bis-bidentate azodye ligands

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Twelve dinuclear metal complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with two bis-bidentate azodye ligands have been synthesized. Both the Co and Ni complexes are octahedral, the Cu complexes distorted octahedral and the Zn, Cd and Hg complexes tetrahedral with both the ligands. All the complexes are dimeric in nature.

In continuation of our studies on the metal complexes of multidentate chelating azodyes, we report here the preparation of two new doubly bidentate azodyes and twelve metal complexes with bivalent Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg ions.

Results and Discussion

The polymeric complexes have the compositions [M₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆], [M'₂LCl₂(H₂O)₂], [M₂L'(H₂O)₈], and [M'₂L'(H₂O)₄], where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, M' = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}; LH₂ = 4-(4-phenylthiazolyl-2-azo)-1-hydroxy-2-sulfonic acid, L'H₄ = 4,4-bis(3-carboxy-4-hydroxynaphthyl-1-azo)biphenyl.

All the complexes are stable at room temperature upto 130°, indicating coordinated nature of the water molecules. They are amorphous in nature and insoluble in common organic solvents but feebly soluble in dimethylformamide. The non-electrolytic nature of solutions of complexes is indicated from the low Λ_M values (3.5–5.8 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹).

IR bands of the ligands at 3400 (LH₂) and 3315–3352 cm⁻¹ (L'H₄) assigned to intramolecular O–H···O hydrogen bonding and their absence in the metal chelates show deprotonation of naphtholic protons, thereby indicating their bonding to the metal ions. The ligand bands at 1555 (LH₂) and 1554 cm⁻¹ (L'H₄) can be attributed to $\nu_{N=N}$ vibration¹. The bathochromic shift (5–10 cm⁻¹) of this band in the complexes is found with LH₂. The ligand (LH₂) band at 1615 cm⁻¹ (C=N of thiazole moiety) shifted to the ~1590 cm⁻¹ region in the metal complexes, indicating the coordination of endocyclic nitrogen atom to the metal ion². The ν_{C-O} ligand bands at 1260 (LH₂) and 1262 cm⁻¹ (L'H₄) underwent downward shift (20–40 cm⁻¹) in the complexes, indicating the bonding of naphtholic oxygen atom to the metal atom³. In the ligands, the ν_{as} (COO⁻) and ν_s (COO⁻) bands appear at 1770 and 1446 cm⁻¹ (LH₂) and 1701 and 1415 cm⁻¹ (L'H₄), respectively, and these bands are observed at 1650 and 1440 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes with a difference ($\Delta\nu$) of ~200 cm⁻¹ in support of monodentate

nature of the carboxylate groups⁴. In all the metal complexes, the bands at 3174–3491 and 830–840 cm⁻¹, assignable to OH stretching and rocking vibrations, respectively, show the presence of coordinated water molecules in the complexes. The evidence of the bonding of the ligands to the metal ions is proved by the appearance of ν_{M-O} in LH₂ and L'H₄ and ν_{M-N} in LH₂ only at ca 418 and ca 520 cm⁻¹, respectively⁶.

The μ_{eff} values of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are found to be 5.0, 3.1 and 1.80 B.M., indicating the presence of three, two and one unpaired electrons, respectively.

The electronic spectra of the two Co^{II} complexes reveal four bands at 8650, 17195, 19830 and 31190 cm⁻¹. The last band may be a CT band and the first three bands may be attributed to $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $\rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, in conformity with an octahedral stereochemistry⁷. In case of the Ni^{II} complexes, four bands observed at ca 11130, 15190, 23780 and 32450 cm⁻¹, are assigned respectively to $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$, $\rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ and CT transitions in a distorted octahedral symmetry field⁸. Two Cu^{II} complexes show a broad asymmetric band at 14105–14870 cm⁻¹ along with CT band at 29550 cm⁻¹. The ligand field band can be assigned to the transition $^2E_g \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}$ in a distorted octahedral symmetry⁹.

ESR spectra of the polycrystalline Cu^{II} complexes [Cu₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆] and [Cu₂L'(H₂O)₈] at X-band (RT) reveal the g_{av} values 2.0892 and 2.0863, respectively. The g values (<2.3) indicate the covalent nature of the metal-ligand bond. These values are consistent with the mixed Cu–N and Cu–O bonded Cu complexes¹⁰.

The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are dinuclear four coordinated with a tetrahedral geometry around the metal ion, based on analytical and IR spectral data.

Hence both the azodyes behave as doubly bidentate ligands. The ligand LH₂ coordinates to the metal ion

through phenolic oxygen, carboxyl oxygen, azo nitrogen and thiazole nitrogen atoms. Ligand $L'H_4$ coordinates to the metal ion through both phenolic and carboxyl oxygen atoms.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B.D.H. make. The ligand (LH_2) was prepared by the coupling reaction of diazonium chloride obtained from 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole with 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid at 0° and the other ligand ($L'H_4$) was prepared by the coupling reaction of the diazonium chloride of benzidine with the same aromatic hydroxy compound at 0° .

A mixture of ethanolic solution of the metal chloride and azodye (in 2 : 1 molar ratio) was refluxed for 0.5 h. On cooling, conc. NH_4OH was added dropwise and the resulting metal complexes were washed with ethanol, ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Metal contents were estimated by standard methods. C, H and N were analysed using M.L.W. microelementary CHN analyser. Conductance was measured in 10^{-3} M DMF solution of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility was

measured by Gouy method. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Hilger and Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer and ESR spectra of the copper complexes (polycrystalline) at RT on a Varian E_4 spectrometer.

References

1. R. B. King, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 300.
2. L. Mishra, V. K. Singh and V. C. Agarwal, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1992, **4**, 333.
3. S. K. Mahapatra and B. K. Das, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 272.
4. N. F. Curtius, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **4**, 1579.
5. I. Gamo, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1961, **34**, 740.
6. J. R. Ferraro, "Low Frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1971.
7. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1960; A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
8. L. Sacconi, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **18**, 73.
9. S. Yamada, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 415.
10. D. Kivelson and R. Neiman, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 149.